

A Homeopathic Case Report Towards Acute Gastritis

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Abstract

Acute gastritis is an inflammatory condition of the gastric mucosa that often presents with abdominal pain, nausea, loss of appetite, and digestive disturbances. A case of acute gastritis following ingestion of indigestible food was managed successfully with individualized homeopathic prescription based on repertorization. The patient presented with dull aching abdominal pain, nausea after meals, dryness of throat, diminished appetite, indigestion, and bitter taste in mouth, with aggravation around 2 pm and amelioration by rest. Repertorial analysis pointed towards *Sulphur* as the most indicated remedy, which was prescribed in 200C potency. Follow-up showed progressive improvement: nausea and dryness of throat subsided, appetite increased, and bitter taste disappeared. Complete recovery was achieved within a short duration, confirmed on subsequent follow-up. This case highlights the importance of repertorial analysis and similimum selection in acute conditions, demonstrating the role of homeopathy in effectively managing acute gastritis.

Keywords: Acute gastritis, repertorization, homoeopathy, abdominal pain, Sulphur

Introduction

Any (histologically verified) inflammation of the stomach mucosa is referred to as gastritis. The epidemiology of *Helicobacter pylori* (H. pylori) infection, which affects roughly 50% of the world's population, including gastritis. Although more precise epidemiological data is not available, the prevalence of gastritis globally constantly correlates with people's socioeconomic standing. Clinical examination, endoscopy (using standardized biopsy methods), serology (looking for pepsinogens and antibodies against infectious agents and / or auto-antigens), and histology are all used to evaluate gastritis and differentiate between nonatrophic and atrophic gastritis¹⁻⁵. A substantial amount of data suggests that the main risk factor for the development of intestinal - type (or so-called "epidemic") gastric cancer (GC) is gastric atrophy⁶⁻¹². Gastric mucosal atrophy (with and without intestinal metaplasia) is regarded as the "field cancerization" that occurs when stomach cancer develops. The neoplastic transformation of intestinalized glands can occur non-invasively or intraepithelial neoplasia (abbreviated as IEN and NiN), which may progress to invasive adenocarcinoma¹³⁻¹⁷. While intestinal metaplasia may also be reversible (after eliminating the H. pylori infection and/or employing chemoprevention techniques), there is little chance of stopping the development of NiN to cancer; high-grade NiN almost always develops into (or coexists with) invasive adenocarcinoma^{4,11}. The generally used nomenclature for gastritis is still inconsistent, notwithstanding the increased uniformity brought about by the Sydney System and its revised 1996 Houston version. Even experts are frequently disturbed by the widespread use of non-standard histology reporting formats for gastritis. It is challenging to

select individuals for clinico / endoscopic surveillance due to histological criteria^{8,10,18-24}.

An international group of gastroenterologists and pathologists known as the Operative Link for Gastritis Assessment [OLGA] has proposed a system for reporting gastritis in terms of stage called the OLGA Staging System. This system organizes the histological phenotypes of gastritis along a scale of progressively increasing gastric cancer risk, from the lowest (OLGA stage 0) to the highest (OLGA stage IV), building on current knowledge of the natural history of gastritis and the associated cancer risk²⁵⁻³¹. This staging approach, which was effectively implemented for chronic hepatitis histology reporting, is derived from the terminology used in cancer and applies to gastritis^{32,33}. Similar to how a specific quantity of portal tracts is necessary for precise staging A clear biopsy sampling procedure (as advised by the Sydney System) is a "minimum prerequisite" for the accurate staging of gastritis in cases with hepatitis^{21,34-36}. A case of Acute gastritis is being presented in this paper.

Case Description

Acute case

Presenting Complaints

- Causation: after eating indigestible food items
- Dull aching pain over whole abdomen (since 2 days)
- Nausea after taking meal and cold foods at 2 pm
- Dryness of the throat
- Appetite diminished
- Indigestion of foods, which may cause vomiting, nausea
- Bitter taste in mouth
- Concomitants: No such

- Modalities:
- Aggravation from eating, cold drinks, hot weather, at 2pm afternoon
- Amelioration: Rest, lying down, evening

REPERTORIZATION

SOFTWARE: Homeopathic Repertory

EVALUATION OF SYMPTOMS

- Dull aching pain over whole abdomen (since 2 days)
- Nausea after taking meal and cold foods at 2 pm
- Dryness of the throat
- Appetite diminished
- Indigestion of foods, which may cause vomiting, nausea
- Bitter taste in mouth
- Aggravation At 2pm afternoon

RUBRICS

1. ABDOMEN, PAIN, aching, dull, afternoon, 2:00 pm
2. MOUTH, TASTE, bitter
3. STOMACH, APPETITE, Diminished
4. STOMACH, INDIGESTION
5. STOMACH, NAUSEA, afternoon, 2:00 pm
6. THROAT, DRYNESS

REMEDIES LIST

1. Sulph || Sulphur|| S:5 R:11
2. Alum || Alumina, Aluminium oxydata|| S:4 R:10
3. Lyc || Lycopodium clavatum|| S:4 R:10
4. Puls || Pulsatilla nigricans|| S:4 R:10
5. Carb-v || Carbo vegetabilis|| S:4 R:9
6. Chel || Chelidonium majus|| S:4 R:9
7. Merc || Mercurius solubilis Hahnemanni|| S:4 R:9
8. Nat-m || Natrum muriaticum|| S:4 R:9
9. Nux-v || Nux vomica|| S:4 R:9
10. Ars || Arsenicum album|| S:4 R:8
11. Bar-c || Baryta carbonica|| S:4 R:8
12. Chin || China officinalis|| S:4 R:8
13. Lach || Lachesis muta|| S:4 R:8
14. Nat-c || Natrum carbonicum|| S:4 R:8
15. Nux-m || Nux moschata|| S:4 R:8
16. Sep || Sepia succus|| S:4 R:8
17. Bar-m || Baryta muriatica|| S:4 R:7
18. Calc || Calcareo carbonica Hahnemanni|| S:3 R:8
19. Hydr || Hydrastis canadensis|| S:4 R:7
20. Petr || Petroleum|| S:4 R:7
21. Caust || Causticum Hahnemanni|| S:3 R:7
22. Coloc || Colocynthis|| S:3 R:7
23. Hep || Hepar sulphuris calcareum|| S:3 R:7
24. Ign || Ignatia amara|| S:4 R:6
25. Op || Opium|| S:4 R:6

DRUG FILTRATION

Sulph || Sulphur|| S:5 R:11

(S: SYMPTOMS COVERED, R:RANK)

PRESCRIPTION**RX**

1. Sulphur 200 ½ DM (LIQUID)

3drops liquid mix in half pure water taken for twice a day upto 3 days only

First Follow up

1. Slight relief in nausea after eating and cold drinks
2. Slight improvement in dryness of throat
3. Bitter taste in mouth persist
4. Slight improvement in appetite

Advice

1. Take plenty diet
2. Avoid oily, spicy, junk food items
3. Intake of water increased
4. Intake of green leafy vegetables
5. Intake of banana for stomach discomfort

Prescription First Follow Up**RX**

1. Sulphur 200 ½ DM (LIQUID)

3drops liquid mix in half pure water taken for twice a day up to 3 days only

Second Follow up

1. Relief in nausea after eating and cold drinks
2. Improvement in dryness of throat
3. No Bitter taste in mouth
4. Appetite increased

RX

1. PLACEBO 200 ½ dm Pills

Twice a day up to 4 days, three pills taken at a time

Discussion

Homoeopathic repertorization plays a major role for selecting most simillimum medicine for cure the pathological conditions with shortened time intervals and regain previous healthy state, vitality of individual's.

Conclusion

Acute gastritis of individuals cure after selecting most suitable simillimum through repertorization by Software HOMEOPATHIC REPERTORY. It neutralizes the excess acid secretion in the stomach as well as reduces inflammation on mucosa of stomach with reducing pain. Swelling, congestion over the stomach reduces gastric refluxes.

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